

SUSTAINABILITY DISCLOSURE AND ECONOMIC VALUE ADDED OF LISTED COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Economic Value Added (EVA) has gained acceptance as a true measure of performance for entities. However, extant literature reveals limited study of this concept, particularly studies investigating the nexus between Corporate Sustainability Disclosures (CSD) and EVA. This study investigated the effect of CSD on EVA and the moderating role of firm size in this relationship. The population of the study comprises 152 firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31 December 2021. A sample of 32 firms was selected across sectors based on the inclusion criteria that the companies would have been listed on the NGX through the period of the study – 2012 to 2021 (10 years) and would have published sustainability reports either integrated or standalone within this period. *Ex-post facto* research design was adopted. Data extracted from the sustainability and annual reports of the firms were content analysed. Data analysis employed descriptive and inferential (multiple regression) statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Results indicated a significant joint effect of CSD pillars – economic, environmental and social - on EVA. The individual effects were mixed. Firm size exerted significant moderating effect on the relationship. It is recommended that managers of firms should leverage on the insights from this study to craft sustainability policies that will positively impact their diverse stakeholders which by extension will impact their value creation potential while regulators such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria should broaden their advocacy and awareness creation among firms and other relevant stakeholders as the mandatory adoption of sustainability reporting draws closer to enable firms harvest the value-enhancing benefits of CSD.

Keywords: Corporate sustainability disclosure, Economic value added, Economic sustainability disclosure, Firm size, Environmental sustainability disclosure, Social sustainability disclosure

1. Introduction

The increasing discourse on the nexus between sustainability practices disclosure and financial performance/firm is in response to the growing global concern for sustainable development which has brought a new dimension to entities' business strategy, operational practices as well as corporate reporting and the manner in which their

performance are evaluated. One of the prominent value-based performance measures, beyond the traditional accounting metrics, that have gained acceptance among practitioners and researchers is Economic Value Added (EVA). EVA measures the surplus generated by a firm after accounting for the cost of all invested capital. It thus reflects the actual economic profit created for shareholders. Unlike traditional accounting measures, EVA incorporates the opportunity cost of capital and provides a more accurate assessment of the ability of a firm to create value. For Shil (2009), EVA provides a viable performance measure for businesses and is considered to be a superior measure of firm's financial performance and value creation.

Extant literature tends to suggest that firms that effectively integrate sustainability practices into their operational and strategic frameworks may improve operational efficiency, reduce environmental liabilities, enhance stakeholder relationships, and ultimately increase economic value added (Narula et al., 2023; Alabi & Issa, 2022; Erin et al., 2022). Thus, with increasing awareness of stakeholders on the challenges of environmental degradation, social inequality, climate-related risks and unethical governance practices, attention has shifted toward broader dimensions of corporate accountability and sustainability practices (Narula et al. 2023; Adams, 2017). As a result, sustainability disclosures in the areas of environmental, social, and economic have emerged as core instruments through which organisations communicate their commitment to sustainable business practices and short, medium and long-term value creation (Ershadi et al. 2024; Qureshi et al. 2021; Wasara & Ganda, 2019).

Information relating to a firm's economic, environmental and social performance are communicated to stakeholders through annual reports and sustainability reports presented as either standalone, or integrated with the financial performance reports under the integrated reporting frameworks. The Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) framework categorizes sustainability disclosures into economic, environmental, and social dimensions (GRI 2016, 2021) while the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), currently Nigerian Exchange Ltd (NGX) noted four dimensions – Economic, Environment, Social and Governance (NSE 2018). Through these categorisations, organizations are provided with internationally recognized reporting standards for measuring and communicating their sustainability performance. Studies confirm that disclosures of entities' activities along these dimensions enhance transparency, build trust and strengthen stakeholder confidence, reduce information asymmetry and can help firms to gain competitive advantage ((Olowofela, 2025; Xu et al, 2021, Ong et al., 2019, Paun, 2018).

Regulatory pressures and stakeholder demand and expectations especially in advanced economies have been the driving force behind the increased emphasis on sustainability disclosures. Investors, regulators, consumers, including civil society organizations now demand greater transparency regarding the environmental and social consequences of corporate activities. Adedeji et al. (2020, p.407) in affirmation reported that “sustainability initiative matters (social, environmental and economic) are generally gaining attention from business and non-business entities, especially with the move by stakeholders to derive more benefits for their investments and participations in the affairs of the firms”. In response to these pressures Nkemkiafu et al. (2019, p.50) noted that “organisations are increasingly seeing the need to integrate society's expectations into their business strategies, not only to respond to pressure from consumers, employees and other stakeholders but also to explore opportunities for creating competitive advantage”. With the adoption of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the growing integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) principles into investment decision-making processes, firms are under increasing pressure to demonstrate that their operations not only generate profits but also contribute positively to society and environmental sustainability. From the regulatory perspective, the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB), on 26 June 2023 released its first two International Sustainability Disclosure Standards that became effective for periods beginning

on or after 1 January 2024 (IFRS S1 and IFRS S2). IFRS S1 deals with General requirements for disclosure of sustainability-related financial information while IFRS S2 is on Climate-related disclosures. Together they mark the start of a new era that requires companies to make sustainability-related disclosures. Nigeria on its part has adopted a phased approach to the adoption of the IFRS Sustainability disclosure standards with full application of the mandatory reporting for applicable entities commencing from the accounting period beginning on or after January 1, 2028 (Anyahara, 2025). In response, many organizations have incorporated sustainability practices into their strategic objectives in an attempt to improve legitimacy, strengthen corporate reputation, and enhance long-term competitiveness which invariably may translate into increased value creation for the firms.

This study leveraged on the stakeholder and legitimacy theories as strong foundations to explore the nexus between Corporate Sustainability Disclosures (CSD) and Economic Value Added (EVA). Firms' activities affect and are affected by diverse groups of stakeholders who demand information on the economic, environmental and social performance impacts of the organizations and this demand and expectation ought to be met (Freeman, 1984; Eccles et al. 2014). Thus, firms that effectively address stakeholder interests are more likely to achieve sustainable success and long-term value creation. Legitimacy theory on its part argues that firms disclose sustainability information in order to maintain congruence between organizational activities and societal expectations, thereby securing continued societal acceptance and operational legitimacy. Firms can only be good corporate citizens and retain their license to operate when they conform to societal norms and expectations (Deegan, 2002; Suchman, 1995). Through enhanced CSD, firms may improve stakeholder trust, reduce reputational risks, build brand value, attract investments, and strengthen financial performance and firm value.

The effect of Economic, Environmental and Social disclosures (EES) on EVA remains mixed and inconclusive in literature. Some studies suggest that EES can positively influence economic value added by improving operational efficiency, strengthening stakeholder trust, improving regulatory compliance, and enhancing access to capital (D'Costa et al. 2025; Bridget, 2023; Akinadewo et al., 2023). On the contrary, some studies argue that extensive sustainability investments may increase operational costs and reduce short-term EVA, particularly in emerging markets where sustainability expenditures may not immediately translate into financial gains (Ezeji & Okoye, 2025; Atanda et al., 2021). Evidence from literature also suggests that the individual dimensions of sustainability disclosures may exert varying effects on value creation, with environmental disclosures often demonstrating stronger financial implications than social or economic disclosures (Aliyu et al. (2025; Ezeji & Okoye, 2025; Tyokoso et al., 2020).

Firm size has been perceived as an important factor which may influence the extent to which firms can integrate sustainability initiatives without jeopardizing firm performance. Results of studies in this area are equally mixed and inconclusive. While some studies, for example, Ioannou & Serafeim (2017), submit that larger firms, with greater financial and operational capacity, may be better able to absorb sustainability-related costs others conclude that smaller firms may struggle with sustainability implementation due to resource constraints, limited economies of scale, and competing financial priorities (D'Costa, 2025; Nnedu, et al. 2024).

Prior studies on the effect of sustainability practices and disclosure on firm performance used varying metrics of performance. First, some studies, (for example, Obiah et al. 2022; Chen et al. 2021; Pillay and Obalade, 2020) rely predominantly on traditional accounting-based measures such as return on assets, return on equity, or Tobin's Q, while some studies, for example, Emeka-Nwokeji and Osisoma (2019); Egweda et al. (2024) and Nwaogwugwu et al. (2025) measure financial performance using market-based indices such as market value added. There have also been studies that approach firm performance/firm value discourse using Altman's Z-score

and Enyi's Relative Solvency Ratio, for example, Ogunlalu et al. (2022). Relatively limited studies have been conducted using value-based measures such as EVA. Second, some empirical investigations examine each component of EES disclosure (for example, environmental disclosure) against a chosen proxy of firm performance without adequately examining the joint effect of all the pillars (economic, environmental, and social dimensions) on firm performance and value creation. Third, inconsistencies and inconclusiveness in empirical findings across developed and emerging economies indicate the need for further investigation into the sustainability disclosure–EVA nexus within different institutional and regulatory contexts that lack uniform enforcement.

Consequent upon the mixed and inconclusive results, this study investigates the effect of sustainability disclosures (economic, environmental, and social) on Economic Value Added and the extent to which firm size moderates this effect. The study provides empirical evidence on the value relevance of sustainability disclosures using EVA as a true measure of financial performance and value creation.

Section 2, which follows this introduction, presents a review of literature. Section 3 gives the approach to the study; Section 4 presents the analyses, results and discussions while Section 5 concludes and highlights the policy implications of our results as well as the suggestions for further research.

2.0 Review of Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Economic Value Added

Corporate finance literature posits that financial performance gives a reflection of the ability of a corporate entity to efficiently utilize its resources to generate profits, maintain liquidity, and create value in the short, medium, and long-term for investors. Among the metrics used in gauging financial performance such as return on assets, return on equity, operating profits margin etc, Economic Value Added (EVA) is the only metric that explicitly recognizes the cost of capital (both debt and equity) in the determination of the financial performance of a company. It recognizes the reality that an entity creates value only when the operating profits are in excess of the funds employed in generating the operating income.

It is therefore from this perspective that Shil (2009) described EVA as a measure of true economic profit of an entity. Developed and trademarked by Stern Stewart & co. (1989), EVA has been recognized as an internal financial performance measure that assists entity's management make needed improvements for future growth and progress of their organizations. For Bromwich and Walker (1998), increases in EVA, result in corresponding increases in the value of the firm and by extension, the firm's share price. It focuses on a firm's ability to generate returns above shareholders' expectations (Altaf, 2016).

EVA is computed as Net Operating Profit After Taxes (NOPAT) minus weighted average cost of capital employed (determined as cost of equity multiplied by proportion of equity in total capital) plus Cost of debt multiplied by proportion of debt in total capital. Thus, EVA is given as:

$EVA = \text{Net Operating Profit after Tax} - (\text{Capital employed} \times \text{WACC})$. Capital employed is the sum of equity and debt capital of the company.

EVA is taken in this study as the surplus income that an enterprise generates after paying an equitable charge to providers of capital. It provides a more accurate assessment of a firm's value creation potential as it incorporates the opportunity cost of capital

Sustainability and Sustainability Disclosure

The concept of sustainability has evolved over the years and has been variously interchanged with concepts such as environmental responsibility, corporate social responsibility (CSR), sustainable business, corporate citizenship, corporate accountability, the triple bottom line or responsible business. The study of Baheti and Lenka (2021) in this area has revealed an upward trend of literature and concerns about sustainability and the great need for sustainable innovative practices. Uwuigbe, (2011) stated that sustainability concerns the effect present actions will have on the options available in the future as it relates to finite resource utilization. It thus encompasses all initiatives towards the preservation of resources to meet the needs of future generations. Authors, for example, Goyal (2014), Okwuosa and Amaeshi (2019), and NGX (2018) have the consensus that sustainability is derived from sustainable development, which originated from the Brundtland report (Our Common Future) for the World Commission on Environment and Development (UNWCED, 1987). The report presented sustainable development as “development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their own needs” (p.16).

Companies are not expected to pursue profits only but also take responsibility for the impacts of their operations on society and environment (Hardiyansah, 2021). This idea has triggered regulations and frameworks aimed at both persuading and, in some cases, mandating entities to adopt and embed green practices in their strategy and operations. Along this line there are frameworks and guidelines like the GRI Standards (GRI, 2016), United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) guidelines, the Nigeria Stock Exchange sustainability disclosure guidelines (NSE 2018) and the central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2012) Green Banking Principles. The grave concern for sustainability issues culminated in the establishment of the International Sustainability Standards Board (ISSB) in 2021, as a separate organ of the IFRS Foundation, to operate alongside IASB, as an independent standard setting body, to develop sustainability disclosure standards. These standards and guidelines present sustainability practices as resting on either three pillars (GRI 2016) or four pillars (NSE, 2018). For GRI, the three pillars to be disclosed/reported are the Economic (GRI 200 series), the Environmental (GRI 300 series) and the Social (GRI 400 series). The NSE (2018) has the four pillars as Economic, Environmental, Social and Governance. This study, however adopted the GRI (2016) Standard.

The economic dimension involves disclosures of an entity’s economic performance and the impact on stakeholder groups and the economy generally. Matters expected to be disclosed include economic performance, market presence, procurement practices, anti-corruption and anti-competitive practices as well as indirect economic impacts, for example, community development (GRI, 2016). The relationship of an entity’s activities with the economic systems at all levels should be disclosed (NSE, 2018).

The environmental dimension deals with a company’ interactions with its environment in terms of resource use, waste management, energy efficiency, emissions, and environmental protection initiatives. The indicators communicate a company's commitment to environmental stewardship and help stakeholders evaluate its adherence to regulatory standards and sustainability development goals (Adams 2017). The indicators are used as tools in the monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of an entity’s commitment and adherence to environmental policies; they enable stakeholders to understand how companies contribute to environmental sustainability According to Ogunlalu et. al, disclosure of environmental practices is currently seen as a veritable parameter for firms to gain competitive advantage, brand reputation and to enhance organizations’ internal and external legitimacy.

Based on GRI (2016), expected disclosures in this pillar include water usage and conservation, energy consumption and efficiency, emissions, biodiversity protection, waste management, environmental compliance and supplier environmental assessment. According to NSE (2018), this dimension emphasizes an entity's impact on living and non-living natural systems, including ecosystems, land, air, and water and therefore calls for the design of eco-centric business models that support the present and future of industry and people.

The social dimension by GRI 2016 Standard has the objective of promoting social equity, human welfare and ethical business practices. Expected disclosures under this pillar include labour practices, human rights, product responsibility, including product quality and safety, and society which encompasses local community engagement, anti-corruption and public policy engagement. Commenting on the social pillar, Carp et al. (2019) posited that social responsibility practices influence the growth of companies and their value creation capability through both operational performance and reduction of the risk of litigation.

Firm Age

Firm age in the context of this study is taken to be the number of listing years of the company on Nigeria Exchange Ltd (NGX). Coad et al. (2013) submitted that firm age is a metric for measuring organizational learning, adaptation and resilience. As entities age, they accumulate experience that enhances performance and survival. Extant literature supports the idea that firm age is associated with knowledge accumulation and institutional memory that enhance efficiency, better risk management and prediction of financial distress (Autio et al. 2000, Ikpesu & Osazemen, 2018). However, other studies, for example Coad and Tamvada (2012) and Brahmana et al. (2019) caution that older firms may suffer from structural inertia, outdated technologies, entrenched legacy practices that may reduce adaptability and competitiveness and affect the response to rapidly changing environment.

Thus, reporting requirements in the Global Reporting Initiative guidelines and international financial reporting standards are external environmental changes that old entities may not easily respond to as a result of reporting inertia and structural inflexibility, and this may impact on their disclosure level and reported performance.

Leverage

Leverage is the proportion of non-equity financing to total assets and indicates the degree of financial risk a firm assumes in the process of value creation. Leverage, according to Myers (2001) magnifies earnings for equity holders during periods of boom and equally magnifies losses and the probability of financial distress during economic downturns. As Ross et al.(2019) put it, leverage is a double-edged sword, as debt lowers cost of capital and provides tax shield but high leverage exposes companies to liquidity crisis and potential bankruptcy. Leverage has the capacity of boosting returns because of the tax shields that it creates and as a result of using less of your own money (equity) and more of other people's money (debt). The inclusion of leverage in this study is intended to serve as means of accommodating the financial risk that is often associated with the capital structure of companies.

Firm age and leverage are introduced as control variables in this study for their likely influence in the model estimation process.

Firm Size

Firm size is widely recognized as a metric for gauging the magnitude of a firm's operations, resources, and market influence. Common proxies generally accepted for firm size include total assets, revenue, or number of employees. For Saputra and Kusuma (2025) firm size is a quantitative representation of the firm's scale, often measured by the natural logarithm of total assets while Alabdulkarim et al. (2024) describe firm size as an internal

structural determinant that shapes the firm's operational capacity and its ability to leverage financial resources. Ahmadov et al. (2024), submit that firm size moderates stakeholder influence, where larger firms are better positioned to adopt sustainable practices due to resource availability and public visibility. Al-Hashimy (2025) links firm size with the firm's resource base, positing that it moderates the relationship between financial management strategies and firm performance. However, Suwandi (2024) suggests that within emerging economies in particular, firm size may negatively correlate with performance due to bureaucratic inefficiencies. Wulandari and Suwarno (2024) opined that larger firms, in some cases, encounter managerial rigidity which may negatively affect dynamic responsiveness to market changes while Arora (2022) considers firm size an indicator of both risk exposure and reputational capital, which affects investor perception and firm valuation.

Larger firms are believed to benefit from operational efficiencies, market dominance, and lower cost of capital due to reputational and structural advantages (Ahmadov et al., 2024; Alabdulkarim et al., 2024). These benefits translate to superior profitability and value creation capability, innovation potential, and resilience against macroeconomic shocks (Saputra & Kusuma, 2025). Contrarily studies, for example, Suwandi (2024) as well as Wulandari and Suwarno, (2024) reveal that large size may introduce complexity, slower decision-making, and higher administrative overheads, which may offset performance benefits, particularly in volatile markets. Generally, firm size has proved to be a determiner and moderator of corporate outcomes.

2.2 Theoretical Review

In contrast to the ideology of classical economists like Friedman(1970) who held unto the narrow theory of the firm, that the sole objective of the firm is to maximize profits for shareholders, Edward Freeman(1984), in the stakeholder theory submits that organizations should be accountable not only to shareholders but to a wide range of stakeholders who affect and are affected by the firm's activities, actions and inactions. Modern corporations, in the view of Freeman, exist within a web of interconnected relationships, including employees, customers, suppliers, regulators, communities, and the natural environment and thus business success depends on effectively managing these relationships and creating value for all stakeholders, not just maximizing shareholder wealth. Bridoux and Stoelhorst, (2016) posited that the idea behind the Stakeholder approach is that value creation results from the joint activities of all stakeholders who interact with a company through innovation, production and exchange processes.

Though Some critics for example, Jensen (2002) as well as Sundaram and Inkpen (2004) contend that focusing on all stakeholders equally may dilute a firm's focus and lead to poor strategic execution, there remains strong arguments in support of the idea that Sustainability reports are potent tools for improving stakeholder dialogue and for generating inclusive value for all stakeholders. Stakeholder power is expected to have a positive relationship with financial performance and firm value. If stakeholders control resources critical to an entity's operation, then the firm is most likely to respond to demands of these stakeholders (Artiach et al., 2010). Stakeholder theory thus supports a positive relationship between sustainability disclosure and firm value.

Legitimacy theory by Dowling and Prefer (1975) describes a status that exists when an organization's value system aligns with the values of the larger society to which the organization is a part. In this light, legitimacy is a pivotal resource upon which the survival of an entity revolves. According to Suchman (1995), legitimacy is a perception that activities of an entity are proper, desirable or appropriate within a society's system of norms, beliefs, values and definitions. The theory recognizes that the entity and the society are in a social contract in which the approval of entity's objectives is dependent on the actions and behaviors of the entity being in agreement with the values of society (Deegan et al. 2002). Observed breaches in this contract gives rise to

legitimacy gap. This implies that in the domain of sustainability practices and disclosure, companies are likely to respond to coercive (where sustainability disclosure has been mandated), normative (expected social norms) and mimetic (imitating practices of industry peers and competitors) pressures (Ioannou and Serafeim, 2019).

Sustainability reporting is a veritable tool to demonstrating that an entity's operations conform with values and norms of society to which it belongs (Cho et al, 2015). Hence, sustainability practices and disclosure serve as a tool for legitimation (Deegan, 2002; Gnanaweera & Kunori, 2018). Firms may undertake sustainability initiatives for fear of legal sanctions. This implies that entities in breach of this implicit social contract may attract adverse consequences including losing their social license to operate. Entities strive to align their operations with societal and environmental value systems, through their economic, environmental, and social practices. To Batista and Francisco (2018) sustainability reporting provides a platform for firms to improve their transparency which adds to their legitimacy and value. In affirmation of this assertion, Nwaobia and Akintoye (2021) submitted that entities which voluntarily publish their sustainability practices, even when not mandated, in order to ensure compliance with ethical standards of the society enjoy legitimacy and are likely to create value for all stakeholders.

2.3 Empirical Review

Sustainability Disclosure and Economic Value Added

Many studies that have examined the nexus between corporate sustainability disclosure and financial performance approached it from different dimensions. Some studies explored the effect of each of the pillars of sustainability disclosure on each of the different metrics of financial performance.

In alignment with the findings of Pillay and Obalade (2020) that Economic, Environmental and Social (EES) disclosures impact ROA and EVA, Ershadi et al. (2024) documented that sustainability reporting/disclosure significantly affect economic value added and that companies with a sustainable approach to ESG build the trust and confidence of stakeholders and experience increase in firm value. Korolo and Korolo (2023) studied the nexus between sustainability reporting and financial performance/firm stability of DMBs in Nigeria and confirmed that economic and social performance disclosures significantly improved profitability, while environmental disclosures exerted no significant effect. Ibrahim et al. (2021) affirmed that sustainability reporting exerted significant positive effect on ROA and ROE on his study of listed Oil and gas firms in Nigeria.

Emeka-Nwokeji and Osisioma (2018; 2019) submitted that overall sustainability disclosures affect the market value (Tobin's Q) of firms in Nigeria but noted that while environmental sustainability and corporate governance disclosures had a significant positive effect, social sustainability disclosures exerted negative but insignificant effect on the market value of the firms. Contrarily, Clarissa and Rasmini (2018) reported that economic performance disclosure exerted significant negative effect on financial performance, while social and environmental disclosures had significant positive effect on Indonesian financial corporations. While Chen *et al.* (2021) Chinese study found a positive link between the fulfillment of ESG responsibilities and firm performance, the Nigerian study of Obiah et al. (2022) revealed a negative and insignificant effect of EES performance disclosures on ROA, ROE and EPS of sample banks. The authors opined that sustainability practices among Nigerian banks are still evolving and not sufficiently robust enough to enhance performance. Eccles et al. (2014) in a comparative study of 90 high-sustainability and 90 low-sustainability US corporations in 18 years documented that high-sustainability companies far outperform their equivalent counterparts both on stock market

returns and on return on equity. Serafeim (2020) further re-affirmed that positive public ESG sentiment significantly predicts short-run excess returns for high-sustainability firms.

Nigerian studies in the manufacturing, ICT, and extractive industries consistently produce evidence that environmental practices disclosures improved ROA among listed manufacturing companies (Osemene et al., 2016), raised ROA in ICT firms (Solanke et al., 2021), and enhanced ROA, EPS and liquidity, in the oil and gas sector (Afolabi et al., 2024). Studies of textile sector (in Bangladesh, for example), likewise reported that environmental accounting and sustainability reporting translate into improved financial outcomes including ROA (Deb et al., 2023).

Qureshi et al. (2021) in a study of 100 best corporate citizens in China concluded that ESG performance affected market-based financial performance (market-to-book ratio and Tobin's Q), suggesting that "sustained higher commitment to the environmental pillar, consistent socially responsible conduct, and rationalized governance mechanism of the sampled firms are perceived value additive by the market players." (p.1)

Many studies on the environmental accounting practices – firm value nexus argue that environmental/sustainability disclosures enhance market valuation, because investors perceive such disclosures as an assurance of long-term firm sustainability. For example, Carandang and Ferrer (2020), in their study of listed mining and oil companies in the Philippines established that environmental cost reporting exerted no significant effect on either profitability or firm value but when moderated by firm size, board size, number of years listed in exchange, and location exerted a significant effect on profitability and Tobin's Q in contrast with Sichega et al. (2021), that documented significant positive effect of environmental performance disclosure on Tobin's Q without any moderator variable. Issa et al. (2022) concluded that environmental disclosure and social disclosure positively and significantly influence firm value of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, suggesting that the disclosure of firm's sustainability practices can be a value creation mechanism to companies. Mervelskemper and Streit (2017) also reported the market valuation enhancement potentials of ESG disclosure whether published as a stand-alone or integrated. However, Wasara and Ganda (2019) noted the differential effect of the components of ESG on firm performance. While a negative relationship between environmental disclosure and return on investment was reported, social disclosure exerted a positive effect on return on investment.

On the contrary, Dung et al. (2024) study of listed firms in Southeast Asia returned the verdict that ESG performance disclosures exerted a significant negative impact on firm value, profitability, and, especially, financing cash flows, concluding that "proper resource allocation and strategic implementation of ESG efforts are necessary for positive outcomes." (2024, p.1). Igbekoyi et al. (2021), a Nigerian study, reported that sustainability disclosures did not enhance Tobin's Q, with the environmental dimension in some cases exerting a negative effect. The implication of these results might be that in jurisdictions (particularly emerging economies) with underdeveloped capital markets and weak regulatory enforcement, sustainability practices and disclosures may be construed by entities/investors as increased business expenditure rather than an integral part of the business model/strategy that can enhance brand reputation and improve the value creation potential of the firms.

The moderating effect of firm size in the sustainability reporting – firm value relationship is increasingly being acknowledged in literature and requires careful consideration. Some studies incorporating firm size as moderator variable suggest that larger firms, with greater resources and stakeholder visibility, report improved performance as a result of their sustainability practices/disclosures. For instance, Ahmadov et al. (2018) found a significant positive association between environmental costs disclosures and firm size among non-financial firms in Pakistan, concluding that larger firms were more willing to incur environmental costs, which enhanced performance

outcomes. Similarly, Ebimobowei et al. (2025) revealed in a Nigerian study that while carbon accounting positively, though insignificantly affected financial performance, firm size significantly moderated the relationship, and strengthened the performance outcomes. Kadhim et al. (2024), aligned with this and submitted that eco-sustainability disclosure, with firm size as moderator, exerted significant effect on market value in Iraqi joint-stock companies. Similarly, Nnedu et al. (2025), while reporting a significant negative relationship between EVSR and turnover, affirm that firm size positively moderates this relationship as larger firms leverage sustainability reporting to enhance stakeholder trust and gain competitive advantage.

Contrasting, D'Costa et al.'s (2025) study of top 200 Indian firms by market capitalization, reported a positive influence of ESG disclosures on firm value, primarily owing to the environmental and social disclosures. However, the moderating effect of firm size on the linkage between ESG disclosures and firm value was found to be negative, suggesting that smaller firms may benefit more from sustainability disclosures.

Following the mixed and inconclusive results revealed in extant literature, this study hypothesized as follows:

Ho1: Corporate Sustainability Disclosure has no significant effect on economic value added

Ho2: Firm size does not significantly moderate the effect of Corporate Sustainability Disclosure on Economic Value Added.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopted the *ex-post facto* research design. The population of the study comprised 152 companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Limited (NGX) as at 31 December 2021. A sample size of 32 companies was selected based on the inclusion criteria that the companies would have been listed and remained listed on the NGX through the period of the study – 2012 to 2021 and would have published sustainability reports either integrated or standalone within this period.

Data were sourced through the Annual reports and accounts/Sustainability reports of the companies. The study used three pillars of CSD, namely, economic, environment and social as proxies of the independent variable and EVA served as the dependent variable. Firm level data of firm age and leverage were introduced into the model to improve the explanatory power of the independent variable proxies while firm size was used as a moderator variable to examine its interaction effect on the explanatory variables.

3.2 Content Analysis

Content analysis was guided by GRI's G4 sustainability reporting guidelines/framework adapted to capture reporting aspects that are relevant to most listed firms in Nigeria within the dimensions of EES performance disclosures. Disclosures on twenty-five (25) relevant sustainability aspects comprising four economic, eight environmental and thirteen social performance aspects were extracted for 10 years for the 32 sampled firms. The content analysis method employed creates a distinction between quantitative and qualitative sustainability disclosures. A simple coding system was adopted where 2 is assigned if the disclosure is quantitative, 1 is assigned if disclosure is qualitative while 0 is assigned for no disclosure on each sustainability aspect. This allowed the researcher to calculate an CSR index derived from the ratio of the aggregated CSR scores obtained to the maximum score attainable if all disclosures were quantitative.

The CSR index was calculated as follows:

$$CSR_{it\ index} = \frac{\sum D_{it}}{M_{it}}$$

Where

$\sum D_{it}$ = sum of disclosure scores for firm i in year t

M_{it} = maximum score obtainable if all disclosures were quantitative for firm i in year t .

i = represents individual firms

t = period (year)

The disclosure index is calculated for each dimension – economic, social and environmental. This approach to measuring CSR index has been used in prior studies (for example, Atanda et al., 2021; Wasara & Ganda, 2019) The reliability of the index construction and coding process was confirmed by an independent party who randomly selected a number of firms from the study sample and applied the same scoring criteria with regard to the quantitative and qualitative disclosures. No significant difference was noticed in the outcome of this independent check.

The specific Corporate Sustainability indicators analysed are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Corporate Sustainability Indicators Analysed (Reference - GRI 4) Adapted

ECONOMIC	ENVIRONMENTAL	SOCIAL
Economic Market Presence Indirect economic impact Procurement practices	Material Energy Water Biodiversity Emissions Effluents & Waste Products and Services Environmental Compliance	Employment Labour/ Management relations Occupational Health/Safety Training & Education Diversity & equal opportunity Non-discrimination Freedom of Association & Collective bargaining Child labour Forced or compulsory labour Security practices Supplier human rights assessment Local communities Social compliance

3.3 Variable Description and Measurement

The variables used are described and their measurement highlighted in Table 2 in this report.

Table 2a: Variables Description and Measurement

Variable	Abrev	Measurement	Source
Economic Sustainability Disclosure	ECOSD	Authors constructed index	Authors
Environmental sustainability Disclosure	ENVSD	Authors constructed index	Authors
Social Sustainability Disclosure	SOCSD	Authors constructed index	Authors
Economic Value Added	EVA	$\ln[\text{Net Operating Profit after Tax} - (\text{Capital employed} \times \text{WACC})]$	Altaf (2016); Asogba et al. (2024)
Firm Age	Fage	$\ln(\text{Number of listing years on NGX})$	NGX
Leverage	LEV	Total Debt/Total Equity	Afolabi et al. (2019)

Firm Size	FZ	Ln (total assets)	Alpheaus et al.(2021); Arora (2022)
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3.4 Model Specification

The panel regression econometric models for the estimation of the parameters are in line with our specified hypotheses and are stated as follows:

$$EVA_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 ECOSD_{it} + \beta_2 ENVSD_{it} + \beta_3 SOCSD_{it} + \beta_4 FAGE_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$EVA_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 ECOSD_{it} + \beta_2 ENVSD_{it} + \beta_3 SOCSD_{it} + \beta_4 FAGE_{it} + \beta_5 LEV_{it} + \beta_6 FZ_{it} + \beta_1(ECOSD_{it} * FZ_{it}) + \beta_2(ENVSD_{it} * FZ_{it}) + \beta_3(SOCSD_{it} * FZ_{it}) + \beta_4(FAGE_{it} * FZ_{it}) + \beta_5(LEV_{it} * FZ_{it}) + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

4.0 Analysis, Results and Discussions

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics

Statistics	LEVA	ECOSD	ENVSD	SOCSD	FAGE	LEV	FZ	ECOFZ	ENVFZ	SOCFZ
Mean	3.11	0.69	0.33	0.47	28.22	0.65	25.65	17.83	8.62	12.08
Median	19.73	0.75	0.25	0.46	26.00	0.66	25.32	18.11	6.22	11.30
Maximum	25.99	1.00	1.06	0.77	56.00	2.02	29.90	29.69	31.18	22.56
Minimum	-25.71	0.25	0.00	0.12	4.00	0.01	21.45	5.52	0.00	2.82
Std. Dev.	21.91	0.23	0.26	0.13	12.81	0.26	1.89	6.62	6.96	3.77
Skewness	-0.30	-0.22	0.53	0.26	0.11	0.35	0.28	0.02	0.59	0.39
Kurtosis	1.12	2.06	2.01	2.62	1.88	6.92	2.33	2.01	2.14	2.54
Jarque-Bera	51.97	14.47	28.44	5.42	17.50	210.87	10.04	13.14	28.67	11.03
Prob.	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00
Observations	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320	320

Source: Researchers’ Computation (2026)

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics which give insight into the characteristics of the variables. EVA has a mean value of 3.11, minimum value of -25.71 and maximum value of 25.99 indicating that some of the sampled companies, within the period of study, recorded losses (negative EVA) while the maximum EVA is about ₦25.99bn. The wide spread in performance is indicated by the standard deviation of 21.91. The average disclosure of the dimensions of sustainability practices also varies – ECOSD, 69%, ENVSD 33% and SOCSD 47%. Some of the sampled companies performed well in the disclosure of their economic and environmental activities, recording maximum disclosure of about 100%. The average listing age of the companies was 28 years, with a maximum of 56 and minimum of 4 years. The average leverage is 65%, minimum 1% and maximum of about 200%. Average Balance Sheet size of the companies is about ₦26bn, minimum ₦21.45bn and maximum of about ₦30bn. The interaction terms displayed the moderating and magnifying role of firm size on the base line proxies of sustainability disclosure. ECOFZ recorded mean of 17.83, minimum of 5.52 and maximum of 29.69. ENVFZ has mean of 8.62, zero minimum and maximum of 31.18 while SOCFZ has mean, minimum and maximum scores of 12.08, 2.82 and 22.56 respectively.

The data distribution is largely platykurtic (values < 3) except LEV (6.92) which exhibited some level of peakness (leptokurtic). The distribution is also positively skewed with the exception of EVA and ECOSD that are

negatively skewed. The JB statistics for all proxies have p-value of 0.00 except SOCSO (0.07) and FZ (0.01). Thus, it is evident that the data set is not normally distributed as the p-values of JB statistics are largely less than 0.05 supported by the deviations of skewness and kurtosis from the bench marks.

Table 4a Correlation Matix and VIF

Variables	leva	ecosd	envsd	socsd	fage	lev	fz	ecofz	envfz	sofz	VIF	1/VIF
leva	1.00											
ecosd	0.01	1.00									1.50	0.67
envsd	-0.07	0.44	1.00								2.42	0.41
socsd	-0.05	0.41	0.72	1.00							2.31	0.43
fage	0.04	0.19	0.34	0.21	1.00						1.15	0.87
lev	-0.24	0.20	0.11	0.17	-0.03	1.00					1.21	0.83
fz	-0.23	0.53	0.48	0.53	0.09	0.40	1.00				1.91	0.52
ecofz	-0.04	0.98	0.48	0.47	0.17	0.26	0.67	1.00				
envfz	-0.10	0.46	1.00	0.73	0.32	0.14	0.54	0.51	1.00			
sofz	-0.11	0.48	0.73	0.98	0.18	0.25	0.69	0.57	0.76	1.00		
Mean VIF											1.75	

Source: Researchers’ Computation (2026)

The correlation matrix in table 4 indicates that all the CSD dimensions are negatively associated with EVA except ECOSD and FAGE. All other proxies except FAGE versus LEV have positive correlation with each other. The interaction terms exhibit the same pattern as the baseline proxies. The VIF values do not indicate multicollinearity among the explanatory variables as the values are below the benchmark of 5 (Stock & Watson, 2019).

Table 4b Unit Root Test

Variable	Level (None)	Level (Constant)	Level (Const. & Trend)	First Diff (None)	First Diff (Constant)	First Diff (Const. & Trend)	Order of Integration
LEVA	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
FZ	Non-Stationary (0.602)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.001)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
FAGE	Non-Stationary (0.060)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.001)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)

LEV	Stationary (0.012)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
ECOSD	Non-Stationary (0.119)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
ENVSD	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
SOCSD	Non-Stationary (0.224)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
ECOFZ	Non-Stationary (0.066)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
ENVFZ	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)
SOCFZ	Non-Stationary (0.050)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	Stationary (0.000)	I(0)

Source: Researchers' computation (2026)

The ADF unit root test in Table 4b indicate that all proxies including the interaction terms are stationary at level (order of integration I(0)). With no endogeneity issues observed, this pre-diagnostic test result confirms the appropriateness of the use of OLS in our estimation.

4.2 Inferential Results

Table 5 Regression and Diagnostic Tests' Results for Hypotheses One and Two

Without Moderating Variable					
Regression with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors; Method: Random-effects GLS regression					
Variabl	Coeffici	Std. Err	Z	P>z	Overall R-Squared = 0.0614
ECOSD	7.667	9.357	0.820	0.434	Wald Chi-Square (4) = 51.07; Prob = 0.000 Diagnostic Tests: Hausman Test: Chi ² (5) = 2.14; Prob = 0.830
ENVSD	-15.076	4.785	-3.150	0.012	
SOCSD	17.444	11.308	1.540	0.157	

FAGE	0.033	0.146	0.220	0.828	LM Test: Chi ² (1) = 162.88; Prob = 0.000 Heteroskedasticity: Chi ² = 0.34; Prob = 0.561 Cross-Sectional Dependence: z = 1.917; Prob = 0.055 Wooldridge Serial Correlation Test: F(1,31) = 8.762; Prob = 0.006
LEV	-15.469	7.361	-2.100	0.065	
CONS	3.800	15.734	0.240	0.815	
With Moderating Variable					
Regression with Driscoll-Kraay standard errors; Method: Fixed-effects regression					
Variab	Coeffici	Std. Err.	z	P>z	Within R ² 0.16
ECOSD	-123.767	84.332	-1.470	0.176	F(9, 310) 883.43; Prob > F 0.004
ENVSD	149.749	51.335	2.920	0.017	Diagnostic Tests: Hausman Test: Chi ² (9) = 20.11; Prob = 0.017 Year Effects (Testparm): F(8,271) = 2.57; Prob = 0.010
SOCSD	5.505	137.504	0.040	0.969	
FZ	7.608	4.137	1.840	0.099	Heteroskedasticity (Modified Wald): Chi ² = 4635.40; Prob = 0.000
ECOFZ	5.061	3.549	1.430	0.188	
ENVFZ	-6.396	2.042	-3.130	0.012	Cross-Sectional Dependence: z = -1.363; Prob = 0.173 Wooldridge Serial Correlation Test: F(1,31) = 9.773; Prob = 0.004
SOCFZ	0.504	5.046	0.100	0.923	
FAGE	-0.738	0.500	-1.480	0.174	Moderation Joint Significance Test: F(4, 9) = 21.40; Prob = 0.000
LEV	-23.341	7.069	-3.300	0.009	
CONS	-163.870	98.794	-1.660	0.132	

Dependent Variable: LEVA @5% significance level

Source: Researchers' Work (2025)

Diagnostic Results and Model Selection (Baseline Model)

The selection of the appropriate panel estimation technique for the baseline model was guided by a series of diagnostic tests aimed at ensuring estimator consistency and reliability.

The Hausman test produced a Chi-square (χ^2) value of 2.14 (p = 0.830), indicating no systematic difference between the Fixed Effects (FE) and Random Effects (RE) estimators and suggesting that the RE estimator is appropriate and consistent for the baseline specification. The Lagrangian Multiplier (LM) test yielded a χ^2 value of 162.88 (p = 0.000), confirming the presence of panel effects in the data structure and supports the superiority of the RE model over Pooled OLS.

The heteroskedasticity test produced $\chi^2 = 0.34$ (p = 0.561), indicating the absence of heteroskedasticity in the baseline model. The Wooldridge test for serial correlation returned an F-statistic of 8.762 (p = 0.006), confirming the presence of first-order autocorrelation. In addition, the cross-sectional dependence test yielded a z-statistic of 1.917 (p = 0.055), indicating weak evidence of cross-sectional dependence among firms. To address these issues, the study employs Driscoll-Kraay standard errors to obtain robust estimates that correct for both autocorrelation and cross-sectional dependence.

Regression Results (Baseline model)

$$LEVA_{it} = 3.800 + 7.667ECOSD_{it} - 15.076ENVSD_{it} + 17.444SOCSD_{it} + 0.033FAGE_{it} - 15.469LEV_{it}$$

Results in Table 5, that ECOSD has $\beta = 7.667$ (p = 0.434) and SOCSD reported $\beta = 17.444$ (p = 0.157), indicating positive but statistically insignificant effect on EVA. The β values of 7.667 and 17.444 imply that an increase in the ECOSD and SOCSD tend to cause 7.67% and 17.44% changes in EVA. ENVSD shows $\beta = -15.076$ (p = 0.012), indicating significant negative effect on EVA. This implies that increased environmental disclosure is

associated with a reduction in EVA, possibly due to compliance and environmental management costs. This is in tandem with Nnedu et al. (2025) and Igbekoyi et al. (2021) but do not align with the results of Ershadi et al. (2024) and Obalade (2020).

FAGE records $\beta = 0.033$ ($p = 0.828$), indicating a positive but insignificant effect on EVA. This may imply enhanced value creation capability of firms based on experience and goodwill acquired over years of existence. On the contrary, LEV reported $\beta = -15.469$ ($p = 0.065$), indicating that highly-g geared firms have the possibility of recording lower EVA due to high finance costs.

Decision

The Overall R^2 value for the baseline model is 0.0614, implying that only 6.14% of the systematic variation in EVA is explained by CSD variables and the included control variables. This indicates that 93.86% of the variation in EVA is explained by other factors not captured in the model, including macroeconomic conditions, firm-specific strategies, market dynamics, and governance mechanisms as captured in previous studies. Nonetheless, the Wald χ^2 statistic of 51.07 ($p = 0.000$), confirms that the explanatory variables have joint significant effect on EVA. Therefore, the study concludes that CSD has a statistically significant joint effect on EVA of listed companies in Nigeria.

This result agrees with the results of studies by D'Costa et al. (2025), Akindewo et al. (2023), Narula et al. (2023) and Alabi and Issa (2022) all of which documented a significant joint effect of EES disclosures on EVA. On the contrary, the result of this study is not in tandem with Ezeji and Okoye (2025) and Atanda et al. (2021) both of which documented negative effect of CSD on EVA, submitting that sustainability expenditures/disclosures most likely reduce short-term value creation measures such as EVA when implementation costs outweigh immediate returns. In the emerging economies, including Nigeria, investor perception of the need to incorporate CSD as part of corporate strategy and business model is still low that it makes minimal impact on performance. This equally partly explains the low explanatory power of the result of this study as the effects of ECOSD, SOCSO and the control variable, FAGE though positive were insignificant while ENVSD and LEV reported significant negative effects on CSD. This position further confirms the negative association of all proxies with EVA except ECOSD and FAGE (Table 4a).

Diagnostic tests (Moderated Model)

Model Two incorporates firm size (FZ) as a moderating variable to examine its influence on the CSD – EVA relationship of listed companies in Nigeria. The Hausman test produced a χ^2 statistic of 20.11 ($p = 0.017$), indicating that the differences between the FE and RE estimators are systematic; hence, the FE model is preferred for the moderated analysis.

The Testparm for year effects yielded $F(8, 271) = 2.57$ ($p = 0.010$), indicating that time-specific effects are jointly relevant and should be controlled for in the model. The Modified Wald test for heteroskedasticity returned a χ^2 value of 4635.40 ($p = 0.000$), confirming the presence of heteroskedasticity across panels. The Pesaran test for cross-sectional dependence produced a z-value of -1.363 ($p = 0.173$), suggesting absence of cross-sectional dependence among firms. However, the Wooldridge test for autocorrelation showed $F(1, 31) = 9.773$, $p = 0.004$, indicating the presence of serial correlation in the residuals.

The study thus adopts Driscoll–Kraay standard errors under the FE model, to correct the heteroskedasticity and serial correlation challenges.

Regression Result (Moderated Model)

$$LEVA_{it} = -163.870 - 123.767ECOSD + 149.749ENVSD + 5.505SOCSD + 7.608FZ + 5.061ECOFZ - 6.396ENVFZ + 0.504SOCFZ - 0.738FAGE - 23.341LEV$$

ECOSD has $\beta = -123.767$ ($p = 0.176$), indicating an inverse but statistically weak relationship with EVA. This suggests that increases in ECOSD tend to reduce EVA. However, the interaction term ECOFZ ($\beta = 5.061$; $p = 0.188$) is positive but statistically weak, implying that firm size slightly enhances the effect of economic disclosure on EVA. ENVSD records a $\beta = 149.749$ ($p = 0.017$), indicating a positive and statistically significant effect on EVA. This suggests that increased environmental disclosure improves EVA. However, the interaction term ENVFZ ($\beta = -6.396$; $p = 0.012$) is negative and statistically significant, indicating that firm size weakens the positive effect of environmental disclosure on EVA. This implies that as firms grow larger, the beneficial impact of environmental disclosure on value tends to diminish, possibly due to increased compliance /political costs or complexity. SOCSD shows ($\beta = 5.505$; $p = 0.969$), indicating a negligible and statistically weak effect on EVA. The interaction term SOCFZ ($\beta = 0.504$; $p = 0.923$) is also weak, suggesting that firm size does not meaningfully alter the relationship between social disclosure and EVA.

Firm size (FZ) itself has $\beta = 7.608$ ($p = 0.099$), indicating a positive effect on EVA at a marginal level. This implies that larger firms tend to generate higher economic value added, possibly due to economies of scale, reputation acquired over time and greater resource capacity. FAGE has $\beta = -0.738$ ($p = 0.174$), indicating an inverse but statistically weak relationship with EVA, suggesting that older firms may experience slight declines in value creation. Leverage LEV records $\beta = -23.341$ ($p = 0.009$), suggesting an inverse and statistically significant effect on EVA, implying that higher debt levels may reduce firm value.

Decision

The within R^2 value of 0.16 indicates that approximately 16% of the variation in EVA is explained by the explanatory variables and interaction terms in the model, while the remaining 84% is attributable to other factors outside the model. The overall F-statistic of 883.43 ($p = 0.000$) confirms that the model is jointly significant. The joint moderation test produced $F(4, 9) = 21.40$ ($p = 0.000$), indicating that the interaction terms are jointly relevant. This provides conclusive evidence that firm size moderates the relationship between sustainability disclosure components and economic value added.

The results of analysis in Table 5 (Model 2) indicate that the introduction of Firm Size (FZ) as a moderator changed considerably the dynamics of the relationship between sustainability components and economic value added as explained in this study. While environmental disclosure becomes value-enhancing under firm size considerations, its interaction effect suggests diminishing returns in larger firms. Economic and social disclosures, on the other hand, remain largely unaffected by firm size moderation, indicating limited scalability of their impact on value creation. The explanatory power of the model increased substantially from 6.14% in the baseline model to 16% in the moderated model, with a ΔR^2 of 9.86%, indicating that firm size significantly enhances the capacity of the model in explaining variations in economic value added. Overall, the comparison reveals that firm size selectively influences the relationship between sustainability disclosure and economic value creation, reinforcing the importance of considering organizational scale in assessing how sustainability practices translate into financial performance outcomes and firm value.

These results align with the findings of Ebimobowei et al. (2025), Nnedu et al. (2025) and Kadhim et al. (2024) but contrary to the result of D'Costa et al. (2025) which reported negative moderating effect of FZ on the linkage between CSD and firm value.

5. Conclusions and Policy Implications

Empirical evidence from this study supports the assertion that firms that engage in sustainability practices and disclosure may enjoy higher investor confidence, greater customer loyalty, cordial regulatory relationships and competitive advantage which enhance economic value added. Firm size has been found to play a moderating role on the extent to which firms can engage in sustainability practices. Larger firms, command greater financial and operational resources, that can absorb sustainability-related costs, and may leverage their environmental and social commitments for competitive advantage. Smaller firms, in contrast, lack adequate resources (operational and financial) to engage in sustainability disclosures and may consider sustainability reporting as an additional financial burden that may lead to erosion of value. These results validate the stakeholder and legitimacy theories that entities meet stakeholder demands and expectations to retain their social license to operate.

These results have implications for managers of firms as well as regulators. First, managers of firms should leverage on sustainability practices to build brand values and competitive advantage that will result in short, medium and long- term value creation for their entities. With the increasing global clamour for green business operations, CSD is becoming a business imperative that should be in-built in firms' strategies and business model. Second, managers of large firms should take advantage of their financial and operation resources to craft sustainability policies that will positively impact their diverse stakeholders which by extension impact their value creation potential. Third, regulators such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria should broaden their advocacy and awareness creation among firms and other relevant stakeholders as the mandatory adoption of sustainability reporting draws closer. This will create positive perception of high performing sustainability firms by investors and other stakeholders which may influence the firms' performance. Fourth, the managers of small firms should be strategic in the sustainability practices due to its possible impact on their lean resources. Balancing costs and benefits may be essential in this regard.

Limitation and Future study

The main limitation of this study is its concentration of listed firms and the content analysis of their reported activities in CSD. This approach does not capture unlisted entities and the perceptions of relevant stakeholders on sustainability practices. Future study should conduct a survey of stakeholders to obtain their perceptions of sustainability disclosures and their value creation potentials for all firms.

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